

FPGA Based Vehicle Collision Avoidance and Accident Warning Using Sobel Operation and Manhattan Distance Metrics

Vishal Pranao Amarnath Kumar
School of Electronics Engineering
VIT University
Vellore, India

vishalpranao.ak2021@vitstudent.ac.in

Sanjana Bhattacharjee
School of Electronics Engineering
VIT University
Vellore, India

sanjana.bhattacharjee2021@vitstudent.ac.in

Harsh Kumar
School of Electronics Engineering
VIT University
Vellore, India

harsh.kumar2021e@vitstudent.ac.in

Rupam Mal
School of Electronics Engineering
VIT University
Vellore, India

rupam.mal2021@vitstudent.ac.in

Vaarshini Ravichandran
School of Electronics Engineering
VIT University
Vellore, India

vaarshini.r2021@vitstudent.ac.in

Abstract— A collision avoidance system in vehicles is a safety technology which is designed to prevent or reduce accidents caused due to any obstacles such as other vehicles or pedestrians. It utilizes cameras, or other sensors to monitor the vehicle's surroundings and alerting the driver to any potential danger. Advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and collision avoidance works hand in hand as this enhances overall vehicle safety, reduces any driver errors and also contributes to overall safety on road. This paper presents the design and implementation of a real-time collision avoidance system using Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). The proposed system processes the video input from a vehicle's camera and converts the video's frame to grayscale and applies Sobel edge detection on it which helps to calculate the distance between the two vehicles using Manhattan distance formula and hence effectively detects any potential collision. It utilizes FPGA's parallel processing capabilities, reconfigurability and low power to enhance the efficiency and speed of the collision detection and response in autonomous vehicles. The experiments were performed real-time on Altera Cyclone IV-E FPGA which demonstrated effectiveness of the system as the results indicated high accuracy and reliability in distance measurement and collision warning by analyzing parameters like dynamic color variation and background noise reduction for improving the safety and performance in autonomous vehicles.

Keywords— *FPGA, Collision avoidance, autonomous vehicles, Sobel edge detection, real-time video processing, Manhattan distance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Collision avoidance is a critical aspect of modern autonomous systems, ranging from self-driving cars to unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Traditional methods of implementing collision avoidance algorithms often rely on software running on general-purpose processors, which can be limited by processing speed and power consumption. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) offer a promising alternative due to their parallel processing capabilities, reconfigurability, and lower latency. Unlike Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), which are custom-built for specific tasks and cannot be altered post-manufacture, FPGAs provide the flexibility to reprogram the hardware to accommodate updates or changes in the algorithm. Reconfigurability is particularly advantageous in the rapidly evolving field of autonomous systems, where algorithms must adapt to new data and scenarios. Additionally, FPGAs typically have lower development costs and shorter time-to-market compared to ASICs. While ASICs can offer higher performance and efficiency for a fixed function, their design and production process is time-consuming and expensive, making them less suitable for prototyping and iterative development.

R. Dubey et al., 2012 [1] proposed the Velocity Obstacle (VO) method for effective collision avoidance in dynamic environments. Enhanced by Reciprocal Velocity Obstacles (RVO) and Optimal Reciprocal Collision Avoidance (ORCA), VO-based algorithms demonstrated robustness in complex scenarios. Xiaoxia Xiong et al., 2019 [2] introduced an advanced algorithm for classifying risk levels in forward collision avoidance systems by clustering deceleration curves from critical braking events. Using fuzzy logic rules with indicators like time to collision, time headway, and final relative distance, the algorithm was tested in Euro-NCAP simulations against various AEB algorithms. Qingjia Cui et al., 2021 [3] underscores the importance of Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS) like Forward Collision Warning (FCW) and Automatic Emergency Braking (AEB) in reducing rear-end collisions. Using sensor data to compute effective repulsive and attractive fields, the obstacle-dependent Gaussian potential field method was introduced as part of Cho, Jang-Ho, et al.'s 2018 [4] generalised solution for autonomous vehicle systems, the approach emphasises path planning and obstacle avoidance. A novel safety collision avoidance algorithm, establishing a safety time model based on collision avoidance time and environmental factors, while incorporating driver characteristic parameters for enhanced adaptability, is proposed by Zhang, Y. J., et al., 2020 [5]. A system to enhance the safety of autonomous vehicles using ADAS technologies such as Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC), Forward Collision Warning System (FCW), and Collision Mitigation by Braking (CMbB) is proposed by Surya Kollazhi et al., 2019 [6]. The authors developed a multi-target tracking and 3D bounding box detection system with minimal visual information, leveraging advancements in object detection methods to reduce computational costs. Objects are detected using the Canny edge detection method and compared to the Sobel edge detection method by Nayak, Ankitha A., et al., 2015 [7]. Morphological filters improve Canny edge detection, and a contour-based learning technique draws contours for detected objects. A research paper on object detection compares Canny, Sobel, Roberts, and Prewitt edge detection methods, highlighting the Canny method's precision [8]. Despite detecting many edges, making object identification challenging, Canny edge detection outperforms Sobel in accuracy. A framework to enhance vehicle safety using FPGA is proposed by Kumar, Mayank et al., 2023 [9]. This research covers object detection, lane detection, distance estimation, and traffic light recognition, employing Canny edge detection for lane detection and CNNs for obstacle identification. Halder, S., et al., 2013 [10] presents an efficient FPGA-based architecture for measuring the distance between two RGB color images using the Manhattan distance metric, chosen for its simplicity and wide acceptability. The FPGA implementation of the Manhattan distance method is designed efficiently. A multi-session project to develop a distance measuring system with 7-segment displays on a Nexys4 board and an ultrasonic sensor is described in [11]. The project covers VHDL code, debugging, simulation, and experimental testing in four independent sessions. This approach enhances student learning and engagement by breaking down complex designs into manageable parts. Increased population and vehicles in India have led to more road accidents, necessitating accident detection and notification systems by F. Noorbasha* et al., 2020 [12]. Vehicle-to-vehicle communication, accelerometer sensors, and GPS modules enhance accuracy in detecting collisions and provide quick emergency responses, reducing

fatalities. Efficient vehicle tracking and accident notification systems using GPS for precise location tracking and GSM for communication are introduced by Lakshmi, B et al., 2014 [13]. Accelerometer sensors detect collisions and trigger automated messages to pre-programmed contacts and emergency services.

This work explores the design and implementation of a collision avoidance algorithm using FPGA. By leveraging the advantages of FPGA like LUTs, DSP elements and parallel processing, the main aim is to achieve more efficient and faster real-time collision detection. Parameters such as dynamic color variation and background noise were considered while detecting the distance between two vehicles and further altering the user with collision related warnings in real-time, thereby enhancing the safety and reliability of autonomous systems.

The paper organization is as follows, section II presents the Collision warning Algorithm, and section III describes Methodology. Section IV presents Hardware utilization of FPGA. Finally, Section V and Section VI, present the Results and Conclusion.

II. COLLISION WARNING ALGORITHM

The proposed collision warning system uses Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) for continuous monitoring of video input from a car and processing it in real-time. This is done by iterative processing of multiple video frames at regular intervals. By processing locally, time delay has been avoided and can quickly detect changes in the environment. This method reduces latency while simultaneously improving system responsiveness and offering vital alerts that aid in averting mishaps.

The collision warning system is implemented as shown in Fig.1 using multiple video frames, hence calculating the distance between two cars by analyzing a fixed frame and finding the bottom most edge of the car. The video frames are further converted into grayscale as shown in Fig. 2 and edges are detected using Sobel Edge detection, which identifies the first white edge pixel of the car's outline. This process is carried out iteratively, going through each row of pixels from both left and right side. By this the average position of the car accounts for any asymmetries in the car's appearance or variations in lighting conditions. For calculating the distance, coordinates of the user's car were set to (0,0) and the coordinate of the car in the front is set to (x,y), where 'x' represents the number of iterations (or horizontal distance in pixels) and 'y' represents the vertical axis coordinate where the edge is detected

The actual distance between two cars is calculated using the Manhattan distance formula as shown in (1). The Manhattan distance is defined as the sum of the absolute difference of their coordinates, providing an efficient method to measure the distance for this scenario. Additionally, to improve accuracy, multiple video frames has been analyzed to factor in noise or anomalies from just a single frame. Also averaging distance from multiple frames can provide a more reliable estimation of the distance. Furthermore, implementing a threshold for edge detection helps in filtering out irrelevant edges caused by

shadows or other non-essential elements in the frame using non-max-suppression and Gaussian smoothing filters.

$$d(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| \tag{1}$$

Fig. 1 Collision Warning Algorithm

Fig. 2 Comparison of Grayscale and Edge detected monochrome image

III. METHODOLOGY

The enhancement of speed and accuracy of image detection and other preprocessing operations are very significant. The system employs various methods like video formatting, background processing and edge detection to enhance these operations. Fig. 3 shows the flow chart of the implemented video processing.

Various simulations based on the prescribed algorithm were performed with plenty of video inputs having different scenarios using the Quartus Prime QSYS tool. A 5MP digital camera is utilized to record high-resolution video which is further converted to digital format using a video decoder module. Here the frames are decoded with the FPGA Board's reference system clock of 50MHz. Further, the input video

format was transformed from YCrCb to RGB which facilitates image processing making it compatible with the display. Firstly, YCrCb 4:2:2 is transformed to YCrCb 4:4:4, which maintains the brightness of the Y component while sampling up the chroma channels to reproduce the Cr and Cb values, which were absent from the final incoming pixels. This matches the standard 24-bit RGB format of an equal ratio of 256:256:256 RGB, as depicted in (2)

$$R = Y + 1.402 (Cr - 128)$$

$$G = Y - 0.71414(Cr - 128) - 0.34414(Cb - 128) \tag{2}$$

$$B = Y + 1.772 (Cb - 128)$$

To convert 24-bit RGB images to 8-bit grayscale for edge detection, the ITU-R BT.601 standard is used as given in (3).

$$\text{Grayscale} = 0.299 \times R + 0.587 \times G + 0.114 \times B \tag{3}$$

Gaussian smoothing filter has been used to reduce noise and detail in the image, making it easier to detect edges. This filter also smooths the image by averaging the pixel values with adjacent pixels, weighted by a Gaussian function (4).

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \tag{4}$$

where x and y are the pixel coordinates, and σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution. The Sobel operation calculates the gradient of image intensity by convolving with two kernels—one for the horizontal (x-axis) and one for the vertical (y-axis) directions. This produces two gradient images showing intensity changes in each direction.

The sobel kernels are typically:

$$G_x = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & +1 \\ -2 & 0 & +2 \\ -1 & 0 & +1 \end{pmatrix}, G_y = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ +1 & +2 & +1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{5}$$

The gradient magnitude and at each pixel are then computed as

$$G = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2} \tag{6}$$

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{G_y}{G_x}\right) \tag{7}$$

The magnitude represents the strength of the edge, while θ represents the orientation of the edge.

only the most prominent edges are highlighted. Finally, hysteresis filtering uses two different thresholds to finalize the edge map; strong edges are retained and weak edges are only kept if they are connected to a strong edge. This ensures that the edges are accurate, continuous and free from any noise. The above mentioned four steps of Gaussian smoothing, Sobel Operation, Non-Max Suppression and Hysteresis have been combined into one IP called Edge Detection and for the algorithm to find the distance we have created another IP called Manhattan Distance. After the distance is calculated as mentioned in section II, the video is then converted back to 16-

bit RGB format which is resized to 640x240 pixels for VGA compatibility. Then for efficient data transfer the processed video is stored in SRAM via DMA and then synchronized using a Dual-Clock FIFO. Finally, through a VGA controller, the video is displayed on a monitor while the distance measurements and alerts are shown on a 7-segment display over the FPGA board.

V. RESULTS

After comprehensive testing with various input scenarios and situations to determine the accuracy of the distance measured and the results obtained as in Table I. Fig. 5 presents various stages of dynamic color variation and background noise suppression. Fig. 6 presents the hardware setup used with real-time output shown in the monitor, along with the hardware experiment results on Altera’s Cyclone IV-E FPGA board, with the distance measured illustrated over the 7-segment display in Fig 7.

Fig 3: Complete video processing flow of Collision avoidance system

IV. HARDWARE UTILIZATION

The proposed algorithm is tested on Cyclone IV-E FPGA and the code was written in Verilog HDL. This hardware architecture is ideal for implementing a collision avoidance algorithm with real-time video input due to its robust parallel processing capabilities and extensive I/O support. This FPGA board provides enough DSP elements and embedded memory to handle multi-frame iterative video processing. The integrated VGA output facilitates real-time video processing, which is essential for analyzing the video input. Additionally, the board’s 7-Segment display is used for displaying distance.

Hardware components used

- Altera’s Cyclone IV-E DE2-115 FPGA
- Sony HDR XR520V AVCHD Camcorder
- Monitor with VGA support

Fig. 4 Hardware Architecture

Table I
DISTANCE METRIC

Distance Measured (pixels)	Collision Warnings
0	Accident
24	Dangerous
46	Cautious
67	Safe

Fig 5. a. Grayscale image, b. Gaussian smoothing, c. Non-max suppression, d. Sobel operation

Fig 6. Hardware setup and Video output

Fig 7. Hardware experimental results

Table II
RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND COMPUTATION

Models	LUT	CLB	Memory bits	Power dissipation (W)	Computation Time (ms)
Slow 1200mV	3081	79%	1,59,488	0.112	0.35
Fast 1200mV	3085	63%	1,57,321	0.141	0.14

VI. CONCLUSION

The work presented is a real time Collision avoidance system using Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), known for their parallel processing capabilities and reconfigurability to enhance speed and efficiency over other traditional software-based setups. Here a video frame is used which is first converted from color to grayscale after which Sobel Edge detection algorithm is applied which helps the system accurately measure the distance between the vehicles and provides the reliable collision warnings. Testing the same using Altera Cyclone IV-E FPGA demonstrated effectiveness across various scenarios, highlighting the potential of FPGA based solutions in improving autonomous vehicle safety. By integration algorithms for lane detection and traffic estimation this work can be expanded for future developments. Also using systems which help in sending notification to emergency response providers utilizing GPS to track the live location of vehicles could improve the systems resilience and suitability in real life situations.

REFERENCES

[1] R. Dubey, N. Pradhan, K. M. Krishna and S. R. Chowdhury, "Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based Collision Avoidance using acceleration velocity obstacles," 2012 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics (ROBIO), Guangzhou, China, 2012, pp. 2333-2338, doi: 10.1109/ROBIO.2012.6491318.

[2] Xiaoxia Xiong, Meng Wang, Yingfeng Cai, Long Chen, Haneen Farah, Marjan Hagenzieker, "A forward collision avoidance algorithm based on driver braking behavior," *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, Volume 129, 2019, Pages 30-43, ISSN 0001-4575,

[3] Qingjia Cui, Rongjun Ding, Chongfeng Wei, Bing Zhou, "A hierarchical framework of emergency collision avoidance amid surrounding vehicles in highway driving," *Control Engineering Practice*, Volume 109, 2021, 104751, ISSN 0967-0661

[4] Cho, Jang-Ho, et al. "A Real-Time Obstacle Avoidance Method for Autonomous Vehicles Using an Obstacle-Dependent Gaussian Potential Field." *Journal of Advanced Transportation* 2018.1 (2018): 5041401.

[5] Zhang, Y. J., et al. "A safety collision avoidance algorithm based on comprehensive characteristics." *Complexity* 2020.1 (2020): 1616420.

[6] Manghat, Surya Kollazhi, and Mohamed El-Sharkawy. "Forward collision prediction with online visual tracking." *2019 IEEE International Conference on Vehicular Electronics and Safety (ICVES)*. IEEE, 2019.

[7] Nayak, Ankitha A., et al. "An approach to improvise canny edge detection using morphological filters." *International Journal of Computer Applications* 116.9 (2015).

[8] Zhou, Guangshao, Shuai Guo, and Zhibo Chen. "FPGA-Based Improved Sobel Operator Edge Detection." *Frontiers in Computing and Intelligent Systems* 5.2 (2023): 6-11.

[9] Kumar, Mayank & A. Niharika & Reddy, Kethireddy & Gupta, Harsh & K N, Pushpalatha. (2023). Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) on FPGA. *International Journal of VLSI & Signal Processing*. 10. 22-26. 10.14445/23942584/IJVSP-V10I2P104.

[10] Halder, S., et al. "A Fast FPGA based Architecture for Measuring the Distance between Two Color Images using Manhattan Distance Metric." *IJECET© IAEME* (2013).

[11] Carlos Jiménez Fernández, Pilar Parra Fernández, Carmen Baena Oliva, Manuel Valencia Barrero . "Distance measurement as a practical example of FPGA design." *2018 XIII Technologies Applied to Electronics Teaching Conference (TAE)*

[12] F. Noorbasha* et al., "FPGA Based Accident Detection and Monitoring System for Safety Traffic," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, vol. 8, no. 5. Blue Eyes Intelligence Engineering and Sciences Engineering and Sciences Publication - BEIESP, pp. 2838–2841, Jan. 30, 2020. doi: 10.35940/ijrte.e4924.018520.

[13] Lakshmi, B., Savitha Hiremath, and Sanjeev Mhamane. "FPGA based vehicle tracking and accident warning using GPS." *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 5.2 (2014): 44-49.